

Taming the Irrational Through Musical Diagrams – from Boethius to Oresme and Nemorarius

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Abstract. Boethius and his followers used diagrammatic methods to estimate musical intervals with epimoric ratios, they determined geometric number sequences with triangular tables, and they treated the converse problem of dividing musical intervals equally. The collection of mathematical manuscripts Codex Basel F II 33 (ca. 1360) contains treatises by Nicolaus Oresme, Jordanus Nemorarius and others. Images in Nemorarius’ treatise combine number triangles into complex spider webs and they display recursive algorithms. Oresme diagrams make use of irrational ratios. These little known images and their relationship to music theory are the focus of this paper.

Keywords: Ratios of ratios · Geometric proportions · Recursion · Pythagorean music theory

1 Ratios, Measuring Intervals and Proportions

Musical ratio theory in the Pythagorean tradition is a theory of positive rational numbers that focuses on multiplication rather than addition. The mathematics required to address the topics of adding musical intervals and of multiplying musical intervals by numbers or dividing them equally by numbers involves magnitude comparisons of rational numbers, geometric sequences as well as fractional powers of integers and rational numbers.

Traditionally, the natural numbers are *discrete quantities* which do not exhibit metrical structures per se. They are means for counting, and ratios are relationships between pairs of *countable quantities*. Since Boethius (ca. 480–525), arc diagrams are used to visualize whole numbers and their relationships. This widespread mode of representation, typically assigns numbers to positions on a line – in ascending or descending order – and ratios to semi-circular arcs within undirected graphs (see Fig. 1, 5 and 6). The ratio interpretation of musical intervals was rejected by Aristoxenus (c. 375–335 BC), who maintained a geometrical sensualistic approach to intervals not anchored in Pythagorean ratios. Instead he admitted microtonal division of intervals as if they were spatial distances [1, 2, 12]. The collocation “proportio proportionum” (ratio of ratios) [7, 18] coined in the 14th century raises the ratio theory to a higher level, by proclaiming a comprehensive theory for musical intervals

generalizing the Pythagorean ratio concept and accounting for the perceptual space metaphor of musical pitches and intervals [8, 13].

Measuring the length of a line means comparing it to a *unit* length defined by convention – by expressing it as a multiple of the unit. If there were a smallest and hence indivisible musical interval of which all the others were integer multiples, this interval could serve as a musical unit interval. The so-called Pythagorean comma was sometimes considered indivisibly small – at least perceptually. Rather than being a proper musical interval to be sung or played, it served as a *tertium comparationis* for larger musical intervals and pitch configurations. For this purpose, Jacobus Leodiensis in the 14th century proposed a division of the octave into 53 micro-intervals or commas so that measuring intervals comes close to counting commas. [11].

2 Epimoric Ratios as a Measure for Musical Intervals

The musical octave, defined with the proportion 1 : 2, plays a crucial role in Western musical pitch systems. Pitches one or more octaves apart are usually considered closely related to each other and – presented simultaneously – they often seem to merge to a single sound. Traditional harmonic theory is developed to a wide extent within the frame of an octave. *Epimoric ratios* are fractions defined by successive numbers. Throughout the course of history epimoric ratios of small numbers were used to explain the perceptual phenomenon of consonance. All internal ratios within the proportion 12 : 9 : 8 : 6 are epimoric because of $12/8 = 9/6 = 3/2$, $12/9 = 8/6 = 4/3$. In medieval source this division of the octave, which relates the whole tone to the consonances within the octave, is frequently visualized with a symmetric arc diagrams (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Symmetric division of the octave Aa into two fourths, AD and Ea, and a whole tone DE. Connecting arcs corresponds to adding musical intervals.

The epimoric ratios can be used to partition the “octave space”. Because they form a sequence of decreasing rational numbers approaching one (the unison)

$$2/1 > 3/2 > 4/3 > 5/4 > \dots$$

they provided a convenient way to measure and compare small musical intervals at a time where decimal fractions and logarithms were not yet invented. A method to find for a given interval the closest epimoric ratios was described by Boethius and sometimes

visualized in medieval treatises (see Fig. 2). Walter Odington (ca. 1253–1328) in *De speculatione musice* illustrates the estimation of the Pythagorean comma.

$$75/74 < 531,441/524,288 < 74/73$$

in this way [17].

Fig. 2. Epimoric estimation for the Pythagorean semitone. The terms 243 and 256 are compared with multiples of their difference. Therefore, $20/19 < 256/243 < 19/18$.

The horizontal lines represent monochord strings of equal length l and tension, the ticks are fret positions for the respective sounds. The reasoning uses the difference of the terms under consideration (13 for the semitone, 7153 for the Pythagorean comma) and compares the terms with the closest multiples of the difference [4].

3 Boethius Triangles and Nemorarius Webs

The medieval copies of Boethius’ writings on arithmetic and music contain matrix like triangular tables of numbers (see Fig. 3). They are diagrammatical tools to calculate geometrical sequences of epimoric common factors. We call them *Boethius triangles* although they probably go back to Nicomachus of Gerasa, a main source for Boethius’ writings on arithmetic and music [9].

1	8	64	512	4096	32,768	262,144
	9	72	576	4608	36,864	294,912
		81	648	5184	41,472	331,776
			729	5832	46,656	373,248
				6,561	52,488	419,904
	a	$8a$			59,049	472,392
		$9a$	$+a$			531,441

Fig. 3. Boethius triangle for the common ratio 9/8. The small interpretive diagram at the bottom shows that the table can be created from the numbers in the first row with additions only (a stands for the value in any cell).

The numbers in the last column contain the proportion for a pile of six Pythagorean tones (9/8). The quotient of the last term of this column (531,441) and twice the first ($2 \times 262,144 = 524,288$) defines the Pythagorean comma, the tiny difference between six

tones and an octave: 531,441/524,288. It was explained in the previous section that it is of similar size as the epimoric intervals for 75/74 and 74/73.

Beside the powers of 8 in the first row there are no further multiplications required in order to create the table at arbitrary depth. Medieval copies of Boethius’ writings and related texts usually have diagrams for the common factors 3/2, 4/3 and 5/4, sometimes also for 9/8 as for example an early 10th century copy of Boethius’ “De institutione musica” [5].

The positions of the matrix elements viewed as locations in a (discrete) system of coordinates permit a geometric interpretation of the related interval arithmetic. Hereby, vector addition corresponds to the addition of musical intervals, and the multiplication of a vector by an integer is equivalent with the multiplied musical interval vector of the same direction. In other words, the tables can serve as two dimensional look-up tables for various geometric sequences and combinations of intervals. This interpretation is implied in some medieval triangles for the common factor 3/2 used to describe binary and ternary rhythmic divisions [14, 20].

Fig. 4. Nemorarius combines three Boethius triangles for “dupli” (2/1), “sesquialteri” (3/2) and “sesquiteri” (4/3) to a web of geometric sequences. The lower part of the picture is an early “Pascal triangle”. **Source:** Basel Universitätsbibliothek (UBH F II 33, fol. 83r).

A diagram by Jordanus Nemorarius [15] shows that the totality of the Boethius triangles can be calculated iteratively and completely without multiplication (see Fig. 4).

The left part serves to calculate the powers of 2, the octaves. The powers of 2 can be used to calculate the sequences for the fifths (3/2) in the middle and the powers of 3, which in turn can be used to calculate the sequences of fourths (4/3) and powers of 4, etc.

Nemorarius was aware that the binomial coefficients, the numbers in Pascal’s triangle (see the lower part of Fig. 4), are useful for the iterative calculation of powers when the base is increased. Whereas powers of epimoric ratios can be determined without multiplications at all, the more general case of non-epimoric ratios is based on sums weighted by the binomial coefficients. Nemorarius solves this task for selected ratios with a full spider web combining six triangular parts.

4 Geometric Division of the Pythagorean *Tetraktys* in Theory and Practice

It is known since antiquity that the proportion 16 : 17 : 18 divides the whole tone (18/16 = 9/8) unequally and that the true “geometric” mean of 16 and 18 cannot be written as a ratio of integers [3]. The division of the whole tone A : B “epogdovs” (9/8 = 18/16) by two epimoric ratios “sesquisextadecima” (17/16) and “sesquisept’decima” (18/17) is incompatible with the geometrical division A:D:B (see Fig. 5). By equating radius and interval size, this arc diagram from an early 10th century Boethius copy reveals logarithmic insights into music: The horizontal spacing expresses interval sizes so that the arcs belonging to the geometrically halved tones and labelled “medietas” are equal diameters visualizing equal perceptual distance. The difference between the two unequal semitones, 18/17 and 17/16, is exaggerated in the drawing, possibly for didactical reasons.

Fig. 5. The arc diagram, transcribed from a late 10th century Boethius copy [5], addresses the problem of halving the Pythagorean tone.

Nicolaus Oresme applies the novel concept of fractional powers to the very heart of the Pythagorean dogma, the numbers and intervals of the *tetraktys*, that is, the set of pair relationships between the first four natural numbers, and he ventures to illustrate his transformed tetraktys as an ordinary arc diagram. In other words, he applies the square root function to the set $X = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and to the ratios formed by number pairs from X (see Fig. 6).

Two other arc diagrams in the same treatise by Oresme concern the problem of tripling the cube, and the calculation of regular polygons inscribed and circumscribed to a circle of a fixed radius. They use musical terminology to denote irrational ratios. Oresme’s “*Algorithmus proportionum*” was rediscovered and published only in the 19th century [6]. To our knowledge, his diagrams and their ability to describe finite systems with irrational proportions have hardly been noted in the literature.

Fig. 6. Besides the octave, all intervals in the diagram transcribed from a 14th century manuscript of Nicole Oresme’s “*Algorithmus proportionum*” form irrational ratios [6, 19]. The numbers are obtained by applying the square root function to the numbers and ratios in the standard tetraktys 1 : 2 : 3 : 4.

How Jordanus Nemorarius determined the square root of two, the bisected octave, algorithmically, is illustrated in the “flowchart” shown in Fig. 7.

4	9	25	49	144	289	841	1681
		k	l	m	n	o	p
q	r	s	t	u	v	w	x
36	1225	41616	1413721				
q	r	s	t	u	v	w	x

Fig. 7. Jordanus Nemorarius’ algorithm to determine the twelve tempered tritonus $\sqrt{2}$ from the Pythagorean fifth $3/2$ in an early printed edition by Jacobus Faber Stapulensis (1496). **Source:** Basel Universitätsbibliothek (UBH AM V 8:2, VIII).

Musically speaking, he begins with the perfect fifth ($3/2$) of the Pythagoreans and approaches the tritonus recursively: an irrational ratio, which simply did not exist in the Pythagorean universe.

The sequence of ratios $b/a = 3/2 = 1.5$, $d/c = 7/5 = 1.4$, $f/e = 17/12 = 1.4171$, $h/g = 41/29 = 1.414$ approaches the square root of two in an oscillating manner. This can be seen by comparing the squares and doubled squares of the terms of the ratios, shown in the lower part of the chart:

$$2 \cdot 5 - 1 = 7^2, 2 \cdot 12 + 1 = 17^2, 2 \cdot 29 - 1 = 41^2$$

Therefore, the original ratios are close to the diameter/side ratio of a square. The rules to derive the two sequences of numbers can be read from the chart (and are better explained in the manuscript):

$$a + c = d, c + d = e, c + e = f, e + f = g, e + g = h$$

The procedure to determine the ratios is similar to the recursion in the well-known Fibonacci sequence, which approaches the ratio of the golden section in the same way. Because they avoid multiplications the calculations could be done easily with Roman numerals – as it was done in the Basel manuscript [15].

5 Conclusion

Mathematicians in the 14th century used diagrammatic means to illustrate and explain their algorithms needed in arithmetic and music theory. Walter Odington, for instance, visualized Boethius' ratio estimations based on epimoric ratios with a generally valid diagram.

Boethius used number triangles as means to find the proportions of number sequences whose successive terms form epimoric ratios. These proportions can be used to describe uniform musical ladders and they are suited to measure other intervals. Boethius' triangles were picked up and generalized to arbitrary ratios by Jordanus Nemorarius. These novel mathematical concepts and methods were taken up and refined only in the 16th century by Michael Stifel [21] and Simon Stevin [22], paving the way to exponential and logarithmic functions in the modern sense.

The multiplication of a musical interval with a number n is equivalent to raising its ratio to the power of k , and dividing a musical interval by n is equivalent to extracting the n -th root of the ratio or raising it to the fractional power $1/n$. With fractional powers, however, the Pythagorean number concept is left behind. Nicolaus Oresme was able to formally describe fractional powers of rational numbers and their rules. In his diagrams summarizing the solution of geometrical problems he gives algebraic results in a musical language.

The value of diagrams in historical music-theoretical sources has long been underrated, and only recently have they been duly acknowledged in philosophy [10]. In this text, musical and mathematical diagrams were examined as objects in their own right. The images are interpreted by excluding the surrounding text and historical context as much as possible. The art of diagramming is also an art of reduction – to bring the essential to the point and into an aesthetic form with lines, numbers – and almost without words.

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